

Yield potential

Morphophysiological parameters of three irrigated rice varieties

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We evaluated the morphophysiological parameters for differentiating the productivity potential of irrigated rice varieties EEA406 (traditional type), Bluebelle (intermediate type), and BR-IRGA409 (semidwarf type) through quantitative analysis of plant growth.

We evaluated plant growth during the cropping cycle by measuring dry matter and total leaf area at seven growth stages (see figure). We determined the parameters of crop growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation rate (NAR), and leaf area index (LAI) using modern or functional methodology. Conversion of solar energy to biomass (Ec) was calculated as

Sampling

EEA 406 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7
Bluebelle — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7
BR-IRGA409 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7

Crop growth rate and conversion of solar energy to Biomass for 3 irrigated rice varieties during 7 growth stages, Brazil.

$100 \times (\text{CGR} \times 3.7) / (\text{RS} \times 0.45)$
where RS is the incident solar energy, 3.7 is the energy (kcal) per gram of dry matter, and 0.45 is the fraction of RS used in photosynthesis.

The CGR and Ec were the morphophysiological parameters that permitted the differentiation of the three varieties.

Grain quality

A method to synthesize the aroma of certain varieties of fragrant Indian rice

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Only one fragrance component, 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (AP), of boiled Basmati rice has been identified. We have noticed that an aroma completely different from AP is produced at a lower temperature. It closely resembles the sweet odor of four varieties of indigenous unboiled rice. This aroma molecule has the same R_f value as do unboiled rice of those strains but it is very different from that of AP.

Results were variable when we tried to produce the aroma using a mechanical mixture of proline, silica, and sucrose heated at a lower temperature. We instead tried aqueous solutions of sucrose and proline in a new series of experiments. Results were best when 1.1 g proline and

BR-IRGA409 showed higher CGR than the other varieties; Bluebelle showed less. After the flag leaf appeared, BR-IRGA409 was the most efficient in Ec, followed by EEA406 and then Bluebelle. This explained the greater observed yield, which had the same rank order as CGR and Ec. □

3.4 g sucrose were dissolved in 6 ml water into which 3 g silica was then mixed. This formed a paste that was heated to 128-135°C. Within 15-20 min, an aroma of good quality rice was produced. A solution of proline or sucrose alone yields no such aroma.

Good aroma was also produced using 1.5 g proline, 1 g fructose, 3 ml water, and 2.5 g silica heated to the same temperature range. The reaction temperature is sharply defined; no aroma is produced at 124°C. The rate of AP synthesis is poor, as is the yield of aroma.

By fitting a bent tube to the reaction vessel, an alkaline aqueous fluid can be collected. When trapped in acid-water and thus rendered alkaline, it produces a different odor that is later converted into a rice aroma.

After collecting a sufficient amount of the aroma, gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer analysis can be performed to establish the formula of this new component. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Characteristics of some rice varieties resistant to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

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We evaluated 25 blast-resistant rice varieties from seven regions in China to determine resistance characteristics. Three susceptible varieties served as controls.

Seeds were sown in plastic pots that

were filled with soil. We selected uniform rice seedlings and inoculated them 3 wk after sowing with 50 monoconidial isolates of *P. oryzae* from 20 races. Spore suspension was sprayed at a concentration of $1-2 \times 10^5$ conidia/ml. Inoculated plants were incubated in a dew chamber for 24 h at 25°C and then kept in a humid room with an automatic mister for 1 wk at 24-28°C before we assessed the disease using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Seedlings inoculated with isolate ZB₁ (85-14) were used to assess relative